

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE
SELF-ESTEEM AND TEACHER COMPETENCY
AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Abstract

The objective of the study was to find out the relationship between Multiple Intelligence, Self-Esteem and Teacher Competency of secondary school teachers of Patna District, Bihar, India. The methodology applied was the survey method with self-constructed and standardised validated tools. The tests utilized were i) The Multiple Intelligence Test a standardised test by Howard Gardner. 2) Teacher Effectiveness Scale constructed by researcher. 3) Self-Esteem Test –A standardised test by M.J. Sorensen. These tools were administered on 500 randomly selected Secondary School Teachers working in schools of Patna, Bihar, India. The data were analysed by employing Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test, Product moment Coefficient of Correlation, ANOVA, Regression, Chi-Square Test and Mann Whitney Test. The findings of the study were: 1)There is no significant difference between Male & Female Secondary School Teachers in their Teacher Competency but there is significant difference between Male & Female Teachers in their Multiple Intelligence. 2)There is no significant difference between Govt. & Pvt. Secondary School Teachers in their Multiple Intelligence but there is a significant difference between Govt. & Pvt. Secondary School Teachers in their Teacher Competency as well as Self-Esteem.3) There is a significant positive relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Teacher Competency of Secondary School Teachers.4)There is a significant positive relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Self-esteem of Secondary School Teachers. 5) There is a significant positive relationship between Teacher Competency and Self-esteem of Secondary School Teachers.

Key words: Multiple Intelligence, Self-Esteem, Teacher Competency & Secondary School Teachers

1. Introduction

The concept of “intelligence is a highly discussed topic for all the

psychologists". In our day to day life, we define intelligence. But the definition varies from person to person. A teacher has its own definition; a student has its own definition of intelligence. "Monarchic theory defined intelligence as one factor, a store of intellectual knowledge, which is commonly present to all activities of the individual. Multifactor theory considered it to be a combination of a few independent (separate) elements or factors" (Mangal S.K.2002). Spearman's Two- factor theory involves a general factor 'g' and specific factor 's'. The general factor's is commonly present in all cognitive functions whereas 's' specific factor belongs to specific (independent) functions.

Thus, both the theories hold two extremes. The description of intelligence is based upon one's ability to understand, to think, to solve day today problems and make proper adjustment in the sociocultural environment. Not only this, it is the ability to benefit from the past experiences (Mangal, 2002).

According to Robert Sternberg (1985), a learner's cognitive functioning depends upon the efficacy to process knowledge or information. Cognitive knowledge includes information-processing, meta-cognitive, executive performance, which helps to acquire knowledge. He further provides the example of people who are quite talented in one area and not in others. In that way, his approach is very similar to Gardner's theory of Multiple Intelligence. Sternberg has not focused on single independent intelligence; he wants to develop components of intelligence in the learner to be successful in all the work they perform. He wanted to enhance intelligence in the students through study and practice. (Asthana Bipin 1991).

Howard Gardner is an American developmental psychologist at Harvard University. He gave his "theory of multiple intelligence" almost eighty years after the development of first Intelligence Test by psychologist Alfred Binet. His famous book "Frames of Mind": The Multiple Intelligence theory (1983) provides a broad base and multiple frames to intelligence. According to him any individual has multiple domains of knowledge which are mainly of nine types and

function independently. They are Existential, Naturalistic, Intrapersonal, Interpersonal, Spatial, Bodily-Kinaesthetic, Musical, Logical-mathematical & Linguistics (Mangal, 2002).

Howard Gardner through his multiple intelligence theory proposed a broad view of human potentials, extending from linguistic and logical-mathematical abilities on the one hand, to interpersonal and intrapersonal abilities on the other. However, as far as the broader and global assessment of intellectual competencies and abilities is concerned there is enough truth in the assertion of Gardner's theory that knowledge of at least seven types of intelligence is essential for the true assessment of one's level of intellectual functioning (Mangal, 2002)

Educationists have long been emphasizing that a standard and single form of education cannot deal with the diversity that nature has placed before us. While we understand and relate to differences in adults, we so often forget to look at them while they are growing up. Multiple Intelligence theory is a theory of education which motivates us to rethink our attitudes towards teaching and learning process in the classroom. Everyone according to him is stronger in one or more types of intelligence and hence is talented differently. So, he proposed a theory that learners have diverse abilities (intelligence), so they interact differently with the diverse world. Evaluating them in a same way is like comparing an actor to a cricket player and saying that former is not a good cricketer and then latter is not a good actor. As teachers we do not look at what our students are good at. Our evaluation patterns systematically help us to find what our students are not good at. Thus, the present theory rejects the theory of one type of intelligence, determining that there are several separate mental abilities in a human being. This theoretical change helps in giving a richer picture about students as well as teacher's abilities and possible successes. Multiple Intelligence theory thus provides more diverse learning experiences, to learn each topic, and be prepared to succeed in a world marked by increasing diversity. At the same time every teacher may have a

preferred way of teaching strength. Using their teaching style (in the form of MI) and strategies teachers should suit the student's diverse abilities and attitudes. It provides them with interesting styles that can be used with different stimulation and help them to recognize the dominant intelligence of student and can utilize his intelligence to guide their learning by encouraging their strengths.

1.1 Need & Scope of the Study:

Teaching is a complex professional process. The teaching effectiveness can be increased or decreased by a host of factors which includes teaching environment, quality control, accountability, policies programmes, assessment and institutional leadership (Anderson2004). The role of teachers is very significant in moving students towards their desired educational goals. Nevertheless, not only teachers but a number of variables plays an important role in the teaching –learning process. Teachers are source of knowledge but by no means they are guarantor of success, because numerous variables might play an impact on the way they organize instruction (Chason 2005). In this context, teacher's multiple intelligence have received less attention compared to some other variables, such as emotional intelligence and so forth(Chan2004; Moafian and Ghanizadeh,2009; Rastegar &Memarpour, 2009). In this changing scenario, the learners' need, interests play an important role, so the teachers should be sufficiently competent and efficiently equipped to meet the variety of students' needs (Tschannn Moran & Woolfolk Hoy,2001). By this they can promote the level of the student's achievement (Cantrell, Young & Moore, 2003). The factors which greatly affect the teacher effectiveness might be helpful in enhancing and promoting their willingness for (Allinder, 1994) and commitment to teaching (Coladarci, 1992). The role of teachers nowadays has enormously increased which is not only to instruct and observe the learners but also to evaluate and judge the learners (Yenice N, 2009 Gokci, 2000). So empowering teachers, and to make them aware about their strengths and weaknesses in terms of multiple intelligence is of great help.

1.2 Research Objectives of the Study

The present study is an attempt to investigate the influence of certain demographic variables (Independent variables) gender, types of school, qualification, ethnicity, income and Marital status on the Main variables (dependent variables) viz., Multiple Intelligence, Self-esteem and Teacher Competency of the Secondary School Teachers. An attempt was also made to investigate a significant relationship between i) Multiple Intelligence & Self-Esteem ii) Multiple Intelligence & Teacher competency & iii) Self-Esteem & Teacher Competency.

General Objectives

- 1 To find out the level of Multiple Intelligence of Secondary school teachers.
- 2 To find out the level of Self-Esteem of Secondary school teachers.
- 3 To find out the level of Teacher Competency of Secondary school teachers.

Specific Objectives

- 1 To find the significant difference in Multiple Intelligence of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their Gender.
- 2 To find the significant difference in Teacher Competency of Secondary School Teachers with respect to their types of School.
- 3 To find the relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Self-Esteem of Secondary School teachers.
- 4 To find the relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Teacher Competency of Secondary School teachers.
- 5 To find the relationship between Teacher Competency and Self -Esteem of Secondary School teachers.

2. Methodology

The present study is a survey research.

- 1 A thorough study of Teacher Competency on identification of skills, abilities and activities related to it were done. For this purpose, various libraries and research tools were referred. Based on the findings, the Teacher Competency scale was constructed by the researcher followed by a pilot study to determine the reliability and validity of the tool.
- 2 A standardized test of Self-Esteem by J. Sorensen (2006) and Howard Gardner Multiple Intelligence Scale was used to collect data from a population of Secondary School Teachers of Govt. & Pvt. Schools of Patna City. A sample of 500 Secondary School teachers (Govt. & Pvt.) of Patna were selected using a random sampling technique.
- 3 The above sample was collected from twenty-eight (Govt.+Pvt.) Secondary Schools of Patna. It included 267 males & 233 females, 157 govt. & 343 Pvt. Teachers. Among them there were 288 married & 212 Single, 302 undergraduate & 198 postgraduate Secondary School Teachers. All the three tests were administered to the students in different sessions, one at a time. The data collected were scored and treated with appropriate statistical techniques.

2.1 Research Tools

“Research Tools” are distinctive ways of describing as well as quantifying the data. (Best J.W. Kahn, James 1995) The researcher has used three research tools for the study:

- The Multiple Intelligence Test a standardized test by Howard Gardner
- Teacher Effectiveness Scale -a tool constructed by researcher with the help of Prof. (Dr.) Father Thomas Varghese (Guide).
- Self-Esteem Test: A standardized test of Self-Esteem by M.J. Sorensen (2006)

The Statistical Techniques applied were Mean, t-test, Standard

deviation, Co-efficient of Correlation, ANOVA, Chi-Square Test & Mann Whitney Test.

3. Analysis of Data

Analysis of data is the detailed process of collecting and organizing data or material in order to investigate the underlying facts about it. GarretH.E. (2006) The data are analysed from all sorts or angles to invent new concept about it. An effective analysis requires sharp and intelligent mind of the researcher. (Koul Lokesh 1997).

3.1 Differential Analysis

Null Hypothesis-1

Ho 1: There is no significant difference between male & female Secondary School teachers in their Multiple Intelligence. The analysis of result is given in Table-1 and also shown through fig 1.

Table-1

Difference in the Multiple Intelligence of male & female Secondary School Teachers:

GENDER	N	MEAN	S.D.	t-ratio	Remarks
MALE	267	61.14	6.12	2.37	S*
FEMALE	233	59.86	5.88		

*Significance at .05 level

Fig.1 Difference in the M.I. of Male & Female Secondary School teachers.

The Table-1 reveals that t-ratio between mean scores of male and female Secondary School Teachers have been found to be 2.37 which is significant at .05 level. So, we conclude that there is a significant difference between male and female Secondary School teachers in their Multiple Intelligence.

Null Hypothesis-2

Ho 2 : There is not any significant difference between Government and Private Secondary School Teachers in their Teacher Competency. The analysis of result is given in table-2 and also shown in fig2.

Table-2
Difference in Teacher Competency of Govt. & Pvt. Secondary School Teachers:

STANDARD	N	MEAN	S. D.	t-ratio	Level of Significance
GOVT.	157	222.02	11.9	4.36	S*
PVT.	343	214.45	20.20		

*Significance at 0.01 level.

Fig. 2- Difference between Government and Private Secondary School Teachers in their Teacher Competency

The table-2 reveals that the t-ratio between mean scores of Government and Private secondary school teachers have been found to be 4.36, which is significant at 0.01 level. So, we conclude that there is a notable difference between Government and Private Secondary School Teachers in their Teacher Competency.

3.2 Correlation Analysis

Null Hypothesis -3

H03: There is not any significant relationship amid multiple Intelligence and Self-Esteem of Secondary School Teachers. The analysis of result is in the table-3.

*Table-3
Correlation between Multiple Intelligence & Self-Esteem of Secondary School Teachers*

ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣY	ΣY^2	N	CORRELATION
30271	1850877	18155	694115	500	0.8736*

**Significance at .01 Level.*

It is inferred from table-3. that the calculated r is 0.8736 which is much more than the table value (0.115) at .01 level of significance. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. It means a significant relationship exists amid Multiple Intelligence & Self-Esteem of Secondary School teachers.

Null Hypothesis -4

H04: There is no significant relationship between Multiple Intelligence & Teacher Competency of High School Teachers.

The findings of the analysis have been shown as below in table 4.

Table-4
Correlation between Multiple Intelligence & Teacher Competency of Secondary School Teachers

$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$	N	CORRELATION
30271	1850877	108412	23674272	500	0.4795*

*Significance at .01 level

It is inferred from table-4 that the calculated r is 0.4795 which is more than the table value (0.115) at .01 level of significance. So, the Null Hypothesis is rejected. It means there is an significant relationship around Multiple Intelligence & Teacher Competency of High School Teachers.

Null Hypothesis - 5

Ho5: There is not any significant relationship between Self-Esteem & Teacher Competency of High School Teachers. The analysis of the data is given as below in table 5.

Table-5
Correlation between Self-Esteem & Teacher Competency of Secondary School Teachers

$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$	N	CORRELATION
108412	23674272	18155	694115	500	0.4216*

*Significance at .01 level

It is inferred, from the table-5, that the calculated value r, is 0.4216, which is much higher than the table value (0.115), at .01 level of significance. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. It means a significant relationship exists between Self-Esteem & Teacher Competency of Secondary School Teachers.

4.0 Findings of the Study:

The ultimate purpose of research was to determine the general principles based on the observed and quantified relationship

between the Main Variable and the Demographic Variables.

- A. Multiple Intelligence In view of the findings obtained it was found that most (94.2%) of the Secondary School Teachers have obtained a moderate level of scores in the Multiple Intelligence scale. Secondly, 5.8% Secondary School Teachers have a High level of Multiple Intelligence.
- B. Teacher Competency From the result obtained 41.4% of the Secondary School Teachers have obtained moderate level of scores in the Teacher Competency Scale. Secondly, a majority of 50.4% of Secondary School teachers have obtained above average level of scores in Teacher Competency. Very few (only 8.2%) of Secondary School Teachers have obtained low level of scores in the Teacher Competency scale.
- C. Self-Esteem The outcomes of the study show that 45.2% of the Secondary School Teachers have obtained High level of scores in Self-Esteem Secondly 30.2% Secondary School Teachers have obtained low level of Self-Esteem. Only 24.6% Secondary School Teachers have scored moderate level of Self-Esteem.

The findings of the hypothesis testing in the present study were as follows:

- 1) There is significant difference between male and female Secondary School Teachers in their Multiple Intelligence.
- 2) There is significant difference between Government and Private Secondary School Teachers in their Teacher Competency.
- 3) There is a significant positive relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Teacher Competency of Secondary School Teachers.
- 4) There is significant positive relationship between Multiple Intelligence and Self-esteem of Secondary School Teachers.
- 5) There is a significant positive relationship between Teacher Competency and Self-esteem of Secondary School Teachers.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the findings that as multiple intelligence, self esteem and teacher competency are related to each other. they must be included in teacher education programme. Schools administrations must encourage these factors among the teachers so as to make them more effective in their profession.

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